

A thermodynamic interpretation of strong nuclear force

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Abstract

We present a thermodynamical interpretation of a nuclear force. This paper is divided into two parts. In the first part, we derived an expression to estimate its numerical value using the idea of thermodynamics and showed that it is an entropic force. The remaining sections offer a novel explanation for Yukawa's concept of mass exchange as a force-space uncertainty relation. It provides a new lens through which thermodynamics can interpret atomic-scale physics.

Gravity, electrostatics, weak force, and strong nuclear force are the four fundamental forces of nature that bind matter together at the micro- and macroscale [1,2]. The first two forces are simple in their description and determination of the theoretical value of strength, but the other two are pretty complicated in their type of interaction. These forces are responsible for holding the nucleus matter together at a very small scale, at the atomic scale [3].

The strong nuclear force is a fascinating kind of interaction and is responsible for binding together the proton and neutron in the nucleus. This interaction is difficult to describe because it occurs at a very small scale where it is very difficult to observe and works between charged and chargeless particles: the proton and neutron.

Yukawa [4] proposed a theory and described that this interaction works due to mass exchange between proton and neutron; there is an intermediate particle, the meson, which carries the force, and this hypothesis has been experimentally confirmed and has successfully elaborated this nuclear force [3,5]. Yet, the only question is that there is no mathematical expression to determine the theoretical numeri-

cal value of this interaction. We took on this interesting question and derived an expression to theoretically estimate its value by using the thermodynamics. The motivation for selecting this particular idea is that, as Verlinde [6] demonstrated, gravity is an entropic force, so in this line, we presumed that this strong force might also be an entropic force.

However, by assuming that this force might be a form of entropic force, thus the mathematical expression of force can be derived by using the following thermodynamic relation:

$$\nabla E = T \nabla S \quad (1)$$

here, E is energy, T is temperature, and S is entropy. Now, by taking $E \sim \frac{hc}{R}$, where h is the Planck constant, c is the speed of light, and R is the space parameter which corresponds to $\lambda = 2\pi R$, we get

$$\nabla F = \frac{hc}{\nabla R^2} \quad (2)$$

this shows the force in terms of the variable R as space parameter.

The mathematical expression of this force has a Planck constant, thus the origin of this force might be a quantum effect, and it must

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be working at quantum scale physics. Since, nuclear force is a quantum scale force, therefore, we can use this expression to determine the theoretical value of this nuclear force by substituting R for the radius of the nucleus $\sim 10^{-15}m$. If we do this, we get a value of nuclear force close to $\sim 10^4N$. This is close to its observe value.

Since, to date there was no equation to estimate its value therefore the numerical value of this force is not known. Notwithstanding, its relative strength is known, so we can determine the relative strength by using our derived expression; therefore, the relative strength of a nuclear force to gravity is as follows:

$$\alpha_G = \frac{hc}{Gm^2}$$

where α_G shows the relative strength of both forces, taking m as the mass of a proton yields that the nuclear force is stronger by 39 *orders of magnitude* to gravity, implying that the nuclear force is extremely strong by nature. This was known, so we don't need to go deeper into it. This shows the consistency of our derived expression with other existing theories..

From the above description, its clear that that nuclear force is an entropic force and we estimate its value theoretically. Now the question is, as it has been stated that this force is mediated by mesons as per Yukawa's theory [3], so how can this fact be explained by our proposed hypothesis? How can the existence of meson, pion, and mass exchange phenomena be explained in the framework of thermodynamics?

The answer to this question may be found in the mathematical expression of entropic force i.e. Eq.(2) which corresponds to the uncertainty relation between the force F and the space parameter R , that we can re-write it as follows:

$$\nabla F \nabla R^2 \geq hc \quad (3)$$

where we can interrelate force and space, both as conjugate variables. This suggests we can't determine the force and space, or radius, of the

nucleus simultaneously. This is similar to the:

$$\nabla E \nabla t \geq h$$

where ∇t denotes the time and it is previously known as uncertainty between energy and time. This idea of was used by Yukawa himself to predict the mass of meson [4, 7–10].

However, as de Broglie wave—particle duality implies, in this scenario, uncertainty in space leads to uncertainty in mass; thus, we argue that uncertainty in force or space corresponds to the pion mass, the intermediate particle thought to be exchanged in strong interactions between the proton and neutron. Therefore, we infer that the intermediate particle meson or pion is just uncertainty in the measurement of mass, space, or nuclear force. The atomic nucleus is so small that the proton and neutron both coexist as per the uncertainty relation; thus, our hypothesis seems feasible, though further clarification is needed to elaborate on it precisely. This idea is a heuristic interpretation.

In summary, thermodynamically, the nuclear force is an entropic force. In this approach, the mass exchange between proton and neutron corresponds to the uncertainty in the measurement of nuclear force and space parameters. This provides a new perspective to explain the existence of intermediate particles. This could pave the way for thermodynamically explaining other quantum phenomena and consolidating the principles of thermodynamics.

Acknowledgements: I would like to say thanks to Dr HS for his comment on the manuscript to make it better.

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